

**FAMILY AND SCHOOL COOPERATION IN IMPROVING THE TEACHING
METHODOLOGY OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF THE
PIERLS INTERNATIONAL ASSESSMENT PROGRAM**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10805084>

Abstract. This article talks about the approaches that effectively affect the successful participation of our country's students in the PIRLS international assessment program, the importance of forming students' conscious reading skills, and enriching the world of imagination. Opinions were expressed about the need for family and school cooperation and parents' role models to achieve high goals in the educational process.

Keyword: effective approach, reading culture, conscious reading, imagination, cooperation, PIRLS

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada mamlakatimiz o'quvchilarining PIRLS xalqaro baholash dasturida muvaffaqiyatli ishtirok etishiga samarali ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi yondashuvlar, o'quvchilarda ongli o'qish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish, tasavvur dunyosini boyitish muhimligi haqida so'z boradi. Ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonida yuksak marralarni zabt etishda oila va maktab hamkorligi, ota-onalarning o'rnatilgan bo'lishi zarurligi haqida fikr-mulohazalar bildirildi.

Kalit so'z: samarali yondashuv, kitobxonlik madaniyati, ongli o'qish, tasavvur, hamkorlik, PIRLS

Аннотация. В данной статье говорится о подходах, которые эффективно влияют на успешное участие студентов нашей страны в международной программе оценивания PIRLS, о важности формирования у учащихся навыков осознанного чтения, обогащения мира воображения. Высказывались мнения о необходимости сотрудничества семьи и школы и роли родителей в достижении высоких целей в образовательном процессе.

Ключевые слова: эффективный подход, культура чтения, осознанное чтение, воображение, сотрудничество, PIRLS.

In the world, effective technologies for improving the teaching methodology of primary school students based on the PIRLS (Progress in International Reading Literacy Study) international assessment program are being applied to the educational process. The formation of competitive personnel in accordance with the requirements of the times, the development of mechanisms for improving the teaching methodology of primary school students based on the PIRLS international evaluation program, the creation of multimedia applications based on international evaluation programs, and the evaluation of the quality of education are being carried out on a large scale. . Together with such works, "improvement of the process and means of evaluating the quality of education, implementation of mechanisms that allow determining the achieved results, assessment of students' level of knowledge based on international standards, and implementation of trends related to the improvement of reading literacy are being carried out." [1].

The concept of development of the public education system in our republic until 2030 was approved, and five initiatives were put into practice, including comprehensive measures aimed at creating additional conditions for youth education. Also, to improve the teaching methodology, to gradually apply the principles of individualization to the educational process, to introduce modern information and communication technologies and innovative projects in the field of public

education, and to participate in international studies on the evaluation of the quality of education. normative frameworks were created. On the basis of the international assessment program, scientific research is being carried out on the improvement of the teaching methodology, modeling and design of the educational process, international assessment programs for the assessment of student literacy (PIRLS). In this regard, it is necessary to carry out conscious reading literacy of primary school students based on international qualification requirements, to raise the quality of education to international level, to develop their skills to solve tasks of international studies (PISA, TIMSS, PIRLS). a number of practical works are being carried out.

Reforms in the field of education of the country can show high results through the united action of society members. Especially in the education of young people, the role of the family, along with educational organizations, is incomparable in the formation of competitive, potential personnel. In the development of a child's personality, a lot of attention is paid to the formation of reading and conscious reading skills in the course of general secondary education schools. But during the lesson, the number of students in the class, the ability of each of them to know, understand, imagine and feel, prevents the adoption of the selected approach to fully understand the information given on the subject being studied. sometimes possible. Therefore, it is important to encourage the child's reading skills at home in order to achieve effective results in education. Because reading in the family circle is organized on the basis of reading and analyzing literature (texts) that suit the child's interests, taking into account the individual characteristics of the child. During the analysis of the given information, the child's personal opinions and conclusions are listened to, and more opportunities are created for him to imagine the information that is not given on the basis of the given information. Therefore, family reading is one of the most effective ways to develop children's reading skills and establish strong relationships among family members. At the same time, the presence of a reading atmosphere in the family circle increases children's interest in reading books from a young age, and as a result, serves as a basis for the development of conscious reading skills in them. Today, the reforms carried out in the field of education in developed countries around the world and how effective they are are determined by the conscious reading of students, the correct understanding of the information given in the text and the information not given based on it. It is no exaggeration to say that it is determined by the ability to imagine and draw correct conclusions.

A close partnership between parents and schools has been shown to have a powerful impact on children's literacy development, and family literacy is part of that process. Studies in the United States have found that family relationships with schools have an effective impact on student learning. When the pursuit of education is united, these two areas converge, family and school members become more connected and work together, resulting in the emergence of "family-like school" and "school-like family". will come. A family-like school values each student's individuality and supports his/her development, while a school-like family recognizes the importance of children's homework (acquiring knowledge), allocates more time for it, and it is its own It will help the child to have high knowledge and skills in the future.

According to the analysis of the results of the countries participating in the PIRLS international evaluation program, which tests the conscious reading literacy and creative thinking skills of the 4th graders, children have learned to read and write before school age, what kind of profession the parents have. It is one of the main factors influencing the results of the students in this program. Teaching children to read books in the family circle by family members being role

models is important not only for the development of the child's personality, but also for the establishment of good school-family relations.

Formation of reading culture in students in cooperation between family and school plays an important role in their development as individuals. According to Safo Matchon: "Reading is not determined by the number of books read, but it is reading with understanding, that is, purposeful reading. Based on this, it can be said that the extent to which the reader understands what the writer wants to say, that is, he can understand the purpose of the work, shows the level of reading culture. According to the scientist, the talent of reading is not innate, but a quality that can be developed through education. When talking about reading, it is worth mentioning the following opinion of the thinker Goethe: "People do not imagine how much time is spent on learning to read, for which I have devoted 80 years of my life, but I still cannot say that I have learned." ". Summing up from the above points, it can be said that in teaching young people to read books and thereby teach them to understand the idea of the work, to understand its true essence and to actively apply the acquired knowledge in the way of life, only at school, relying on lessons learned is not effective enough. For this, it is necessary for parents and family members to set an example, to dedicate a lot of effort, effort and time for the development of their child.

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